

Pword-report

Language name: **Garó (LID ???)**
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Sources: Burling, Robins (2004). *The Language of the Modhupur Mandi (Garó)*. New Delhi: Bibliophile South Asia in assoc. with Promilla & Co. Publishers.
Internet version of The Ethnologue, Vol. 15 (2005). www.ethnologue.com.
Date completed: 06.03.2006

I Language profile

of spks: 677'000.
Contact lgs.: Bengali, English
Status: not an official language, but written in Devanāgarī script
Prospects: taught in primary schools, at least in BD, parents want their children to write/read Garó
Struct. results: many borrowings from Bengali, English

II Morpheme types

1. _____ Stem

2. _____ Restricted postposed formative

-jok 'PERF' (with V only)

- (1) sok-jok
arrive-PERF
'(s/he) has arrived'

3. _____ Unrestricted postposed formative

-o 'LOC'

- | | |
|---|--|
| (2) <i>Bang.la.des=o</i>
Bangladesh=LOC
'in Bangladesh' | (3) <i>me.ja=o</i>
yesterday=LOC
'yesterday' |
| (4) <i>je=o</i>
REL=LOC
'at whichever, wherever' | (5) <i>ang-ko sing'-jok=o</i>
1s-ACC ask-PERF=LOC
'when I have been asked' |

4. _____ Restricted preposed formative

sak- 'CLF.HUM' (with Numerals only)

- (6) *sak-gin.ing~sak-gin.ing*
CLF.HUM-two~each
'each pair of people'

5.? _____ Clause-final clitic

=ma 'Q' (used for yes-no-questions, but since always(?) a V is at the end, it appears to be always attached to a V)

- (7) *to-a=ma*
taste.good-NTR=Q
'does it taste good?'

→ 4/5 morpheme types

III Syllable

Note that there is **NO RESYLLABIFICATION** during morphological processes! (cf. rules 4 and 5 below)

Syllable structure

The syllable shape is (s)(C)(r)V(V)(C). But there is no example of a syllable with complex onset and complex nucleus.

Initial clusters:

(8)	/p ^h r/	<i>prak</i>	'each'
(9)	/t ^h r/	<i>tring.a</i>	'weave'
(10)	/k ^h r/	<i>nok.krom</i>	'heir to a household'
(11)	/tsr/	<i>chra</i>	'kinsmen'
(12)	/br/	<i>bring</i>	'jungle'
(13)	/d̥r/	<i>drak.a</i>	'badly torn'
(14)	/gr/	<i>grang</i>	'feathers'
(15)	/d̥zr/	<i>jro.a</i>	'chili hot'
(16)	/sr/	<i>sri</i>	'slice'
(17)	/mr/	<i>mrang.a</i>	'redish'

additionally, an extra-syllabic /s/ can occur before voiceless stops (in native words derived from /siT/ due to /i/-deletion):

(18)	/sp ^h /	<i>spo.a</i>	'blow'
(19)	/st ^h /	<i>stik.a</i>	'cover'
		<i>stu.den</i>	'student'
(20)	/sk ^h /	<i>sko</i>	'head'
(21)	/sp ^h r/	<i>spru</i>	'snail'
(22)	/sk ^h r/	<i>skrik.a</i>	'peel'

Complex nuclei (no length distinction, but some diphthongs (but very rare)):

(23)	/ai/	<i>hai'.a</i>	'know'
(24)	/au/	<i>jil'.au.a</i>	'flair up'
(25)	/eo/	<i>seo'.seo.i</i>	'speaking with a hoarse voice'
(26)	/ui/	<i>kui.cha</i>	'eel'
(27)	/oi/	<i>boi</i>	'book' (but only in a few borrowings in the Mande dialect)

N.B.: The glottalization (') in the coda can be (historically) analyzed as a feature of the whole syllable (it cognates with a tone in closely related languages). All consonants can (historically underlyingly) occur with glottal stop, but with all except nasals and the lateral, a vowel has been copied between them resulting in two syllables: CV_iT[?] →_{hist.} CV_i?V_iT (thus, in a synchronic analysis, the glottal stop is a consonant occurring in the coda, and nasals and the lateral can occur either glottalized or not in the coda).

Monomoraic words

(28)	<i>sa</i>	'who, one'
(29)	<i>mi</i>	'rice'
(30)	<i>spru</i>	'snail'

Vowel-initial words

(31)	<i>ang.a</i>	'I'
(32)	<i>a.gan.a</i>	'tell'
(33)	<i>i'.ang</i>	'go'

Polysyllabic morphemes

(34)	<i>a.gan-</i>	'tell'
(35)	<i>i'.ang</i>	'go'

- All morphemes are at least a full syllable.

Phonotactics

- (36) *_{(σ)η} (/η/ is not allowed in onsets)
 (37) /l/ only occurs in onsets in borrowed words (the native written *l* is retroflex and is the coda allophone of /ɾ/).
 (38) *_{(ts,dz,s,h,w)σ} (/s ts/ can occur in the coda in borrowings)

Superheavy syllables

All examples (at least no other one found) have glottal stop as their coda consonant, which does not count for weight (see above and cf. rule 3 below).

- (39) *hai'.a* 'know'

Thus, there are no superheavy syllables.

IV Tone & Stress

Tone

There is no evidence for distinctive tone in Garo.

Stress

Primary stress (´) is assigned word-finally, but there are some suffixes (the (phrasal) case suffixes and some verbal TAM suffixes) that do not participate:

- (40) *pa.jóng* 'uncle'
 (41) *me'.chík* 'woman'
 but:
 (42) *sók-a* 'arrive-NTR = arrive(s)' (NTR (neutral tense) is a TAM marker that occurs when no other one is there, and sometimes also with others, it has no distinct tense meaning, but is mostly translated with PRES)
 (43) *sok-nó-a* 'arrive-FUT-NTR = will arrive'
 (44) *sóng=o=na* 'house=LOC=QUOT = to the house'
 (45) *me'.chik-dráng* 'woman-PL = women'
 (46) *kat-já-ing-a* 'run-NEG-PROG-NTR = not running'
 (47) *kat-ba-pil'-jók* 'run-VENT-BACK-PERF = has run back here'
 (48) *de-dráng=o* 'human-PL=LOC = by the people'

Secondary stress (˘) is assigned to final syllables of initial compound parts, but not if the second compound part is monosyllabic. Thus two stressed syllables can not be adjacent within a word.

- (49) *bòl-bi.ják* 'tree leaf'
 (50) *man.di-kú* 'Mandi language' (**man.di-kú*)
 (51) *pi.pròt-ki'.sáng* 'a bird'
 (52) *dò'-ma.sek.í* 'a bird'

Additionally, secondary stress is assigned stem-finally, when more than one stressed suffix occurs:

- (53) *dak.chàk-ja-ing-jók* 'help-NEG-PROG-PERF = not helping any more'

(Note that *-ing* 'PROG' is never stressed, but main stress of the whole word ignores that.)

Secondary stress is also assigned to the first reduplicant if the reduplicated form is not monosyllabic:

- (54) *grok-grók* 'in gulps'
 (55) *mal.àk~mal.ák* 'craving water thirstily'

V Other Non-concatenative Processes

nothing found (no ablaut phenomena etc.)

List of phonological processes

1. _____ Coda stop neutralization

/p^h t^h k^h b d g/ → [-aspirated, -voiced] / ____)_o

(56) /no-k^ho/ → [no.k^ho] 'younger sister-ACC'

(57) /nok^h/ → [nök] 'house'

2. _____ Degemination

2a. C_i → Ø / ____C_i

2b. /p^hb/; /t^hd/; /kg/; /tts tɬ/ → [p]; [t]; [k]; [ts]

2c. C_i → Ø / C_i ____

(58) /nok^h-k^ho/ → [nök^ho] 'house-ACC'

(59) /tson-na/ → [tsöna] 'to be small'

(60) /mik-gir/ → [mĩki] 'eyelid' (*mik* 'eye' + *gil* 'skin')

(61) /at-tsu/ → [ätsu] 'grandfather' (*at* 'father' + *chu* 'high')

(62) /tson²-na/ → [tsön²a] 'to finish' (looks like no degemination, but glottalized sonorants **always** have an extra-short copy of themselves after the glottal striction, cf. /tson²-a/ → [tsön²a] 'finish-NTR')

3. _____ Vowel shortening

V → v̥ / ____C)_o (C is not ?, and thus, /?/ does not count for syllable weight!)

N.B.: This rule applies **before** the degemination rule (cf. (67))!

(63) /no/ → [no] 'younger sister.NOM'

(64) /no+k^ho/ → [no.k^ho] 'younger sister-ACC'

(65) /nok^h/ → [nök] 'house.NOM'

(66) /nok^h+o/ → [nök.o] 'house-LOC'

(67) /nok^h+k^ho/ → [nök.k^ho] 'house-ACC'

4. _____ Word-final glottalization deletion

C², ? → C, Ø / ____# (in northern dialects (A'chik) and BD-Mande, a copy vowel is inserted after word-final ?)

(68) /war²/ → [wǎ] 'fire' (but cf. [wǎ²ni] 'of the fire')

(69) /ta²/ → [ta] (Mandi) / [ta²a] (A'chik) 'tuber' (but cf. [ta².o] 'in the tuber')

5. _____ Vowel backing

/i/ → [ü] / ____C)_o (C is not ?)

(70) /bi.k^ha/ → [bik^ha] 'liver'

(71) /bik^h.a/ → [bük.a] 'carve'

6. _____ Even syllable glottalization deletion

Glottalization and glottal stop are deleted in every second, fourth, sixth ... syllable of a word:

in the second syllable:

(72) *kat-pil-a* 'run-BACK-NTR = run(s) back'

(73) *kat-ba-a* 'run-VENT-NTR = run(s) here'

(74) *kat-ba-pil'-a* 'run-VENT-BACK-NTR = run(s) back here'

(75) *kat-pil-ba'-jok* 'run-BACK-VENT-PERF = have/s run back here'

(76) *gu.ri-ba'-pil-jok* 'wander-VENT-BACK-PERF = have/s wandered back here'

(77) *gu.ri-pil'-ba-jok* 'wander-BACK-VENT-PERF = have/s wandered back here' (unusual but grammatical)

in the fourth syllable:

(78) *i'.ru.ra'-pil-a-ring-a* 'returning in a back and forth way'

(no example found for sixth syllable)

7. _____ Glottal stop insertion

∅ → [ʔ] / σ.(C)a___+a (between polysyllabic a-final forms/stems and the suffix -a 'NTR', but not, when NEG suffix -ja precedes the -a, because then one /a/ is omitted)

- (79) *i'-ba'-a* 'go-VENT-NTR = come(s)' (the glottal stop is there underlyingly, but would be deleted by rule 6, cf. *i'-ba-bo* 'go-VENT-IMP')
- (80) *i'.ang-a* 'go-?-NTR'
i'.ang-j-a 'go-?-NEG-NTR'
- but not in monosyllabic forms:
- (81) *sa-a* 'serve.food-NTR' (**sa'-a*)

VI "Free" Grammatical Morphemes

- Phrasal suffixes (= "clitics") are not stressed, but there are also restricted suffixes that are not.
- Prefixes appear to form a single word with their hosts with all rules (at least no other information is given in the grammar).

- (82) *sak-git.tám* 'CLF.HUM-three = three people' (no secondary stress on the prefix!)

- The "less-cohering" suffixes (that do not participate in the word-final stress pattern) can be skipped by the stress if a cohering suffix follows (cf. (53) above)

VII Polymorphemic Stem Forms

- Stress assignment: As already stated, the CLF-prefixes, some suffixes and the (all?) clitics do not participate in stress assignment, thus they do never bear stress (neither primary nor secondary)
- Rule 7 (Glottal stop insertion) only works on morpheme boundaries. Within stems, the necessary context does not occur (no /aa/-sequence, underlyingly).

Special rules with certain morphemes

- PROG -ing /-iŋ/ and FOC -in /-in/ (both unstressed) are changed to [-Vŋ/n] directly after V(?):

- (83) *go-ong-a* [go.ŏŋ.a] (84) *so'-ong-a* [soʔ.ŏŋ.a]
 throw-PROG-NTR burn-PROG-NTR
 'throwing' 'burning'
- (85) *si-ing-a* [si.iŋ.a] (86) *pi'-ing-a* [piʔ.iŋ.a]
 die-PROG-NTR break-PROG-NTR
 'dying' 'breaking'
- (87) *tam.pi-in* [tʰám.pʰi.iŋ]
 fly-FOC
 'a fly!'

in other contexts, they are pronounced with a high back unrounded vowel due to rule 5:

- (88) *nap-ing-a* [näp.ũŋ.a] (89) *a.chak-in* [a.tsăk.ũŋ]
 enter-PROG-NTR
 'entering'

VIII Compounds, Concatenations, Juxtapositions

As already mentioned, compounds form one word concerning all rules except sometimes the word-final glottal deletion (rule 4):

(90) *han.jak* 'body+hand = whole body'

but:

(91) *dò'-ma.sek.í* 'bird+maseki = Maseki bird'

IX Reduplication

- Rule 6 (Even syll. glott. deletion) works through whole reduplicated form:

Reduplication does not cause deglottalization:

(92) *sol'.i~sol'.i* 'by small chops (as when carving)'

but rule 6 works:

(93) *jem'-jem-a* 'repeat~INTENS-NTR = constantly'

If the form of (93) above is suffixed as an adverbial suffix, the absent glottalization is NOT restored, but the first glottalization is then deleted, because it becomes the second syllable of the whole thing:

(94) *den'-jem~jem-a* 'cut-REPEATEDLY-NTR = cut(s) repeatedly'

Sometimes a coda consonant of the first reduplicant is omitted, but all rules concerning closed syllables do work (for instance rule 5):

(95) *ham'-ri-rik-a* [hã^m.rũ.rũk.a] (*ham'-rik-rik-a* is also possible)
want-CONTINUOUSLY-NTR
'wanted continuously'

X Phrase/Sentence-level phenomena

Isolated words rise on the stressed syllable and fall sharply at the very end. The same pattern is found in clauses, the single words have their rising stress, but the last word falls sharply (in declarative sentences and word-questions) or also rises (in yes-no-questions).

XI Other Special things

Geminates: are not allowed, cf. rule 2 above